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ADVANCED FLOW FRONT AND CURE MONITORING USING HIGH FREQUENCY TECHNOLOGY

Céline Le Gleuher¹, Christopher Buchmann¹, Katharina Schlegel², Alois Friedberger²

¹InFactory Solutions GmbH, 82024 Taufkirchen, Germany

²Airbus CRT, 81663 Munich, Germany

Email: christopher.buchmann@infactory-solutions.net Tel: +49 173 3287245

ABSTRACT

Monitoring the infusion and cure during the manufacturing of composite parts offers great potential to increase both process stability and economic efficiency. Using high frequency technology, a single sensor line is sufficient to provide spatial information on the position of multiple flow fronts and the local progress of the cure of the resin. Thus, the number of sensors necessary can be reduced, minimizing negative effects on the process and facilitating sensor integration. In combination with different sensors geometries such as printed types and wire sensors, the technology can be tailored to the needs of a specific process. The presentation covers the recent advances on the technology which have been obtained within the EU-funded project ZAero where the sensors are used as a building block to enable a fully digitalized and transparent process chain.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the frame of the EU funded project ZAero (Zero-defect manufacturing of composite parts in the aerospace industry), inline quality control methods for carbon fibre parts (CFRP) production and decision support system are investigated. The objectives of the project are to reduce production costs, increase production rate and minimize waste and scrape.

Current technologies for inline quality control are targeting automated fibre placement (AFP) process or automated tape lay-up (ATL) process, both working with pre-impregnated carbon fibres. However, few solutions are targeting direct processes (infusion, resin transfer moulding (RTM)...). From those existing solutions, the integrated sensors are invasive and cannot monitor both infusion resin flow front and cure.

For this project, it was chosen to investigate thin, printed foil sensors using a technology developed by InFactory Solutions GmbH, based on Electrical Time Domain Reflectometry (E-TDR). The breakthrough offered by this high frequency technology permits to obtain from one single sensor information on both resin flow front and cure conversion of the matrix. The focus of this study was placed on the sensors size reduction, and thus the minimisation of negative effects on process and sensor integration.

This paper will present the last results obtained in the frame of ZAero project, targeting new sensor geometries.

2. ELECTRICAL TIME DOMAIN REFLECTOMETRY

2.1 E-TDR Technology

Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) is based on the physical principle that waves are partially or completely reflected when passing through the interface to a medium with a different permeability e.g. light at a water surface.

In the field of electrical TDR (E-TDR), this wave is a high-rise time voltage pulse which is sent into a controlled-impedance transmission line. It is reflected at impedance discontinuities within the line, coming from medium properties changes (like permeability or dielectric properties).

The main advantage of E-TDR in comparison to other existing monitoring technologies is that distributed measurements along the sensor line are possible. Using this method, it is possible to develop data across a continuous area all along the sensor line, with a spatial resolution of as low as 1% of the sensor length.

Using an oscilloscope, a profile of a transmission line impedance is obtained. This line is used as a sensor. The X-axis is the time to travel along the sensor and the Y-axis is the reflected impedance. Impedance is then easily correlated to material properties, such as dielectric permittivity.

In CFRP materials, dielectric properties of carbon fibres and resin are different, but also are uncured and cured resin dielectric properties. As those properties change during the infiltration of the part and during the cure of the resin, the technology can be used for both infusion and cure monitoring.

Figure 1: Schematic description of E-TDR technology for resin infusion monitoring [1]

The suitability of the technology for inline quality monitoring of CFRP was proven within a previous project [2]. However, some challenges should be met to set the path for an industrial application. It includes the optimised sensor geometry.

InFactory Solutions' Cure and Flow Front (CFF) Monitoring system, which is used in this study, is based on E-TDR technology to allow an automatic prediction of the flow front position and cure during composite production

2.2 Sensors

CFF sensors need to withstand the high process temperatures required in aerospace industry (180°). They also need to be mechanically robust, flexible and thin enough to enable an electrical feedthrough within a vacuum set-up. However, one of the main challenge when considering E-TDR technology, is the sensitivity of sensors to electrically conductive fibres.

In a previous study [2], two types of sensor were evaluated:

- Flat Flexible Cable (FFC) sensor, made of six parallel conductors, isolated by a polyester film on each side. It presented a thickness of 0.28mm and a width of 4.5mm.
- Shielded sensor, made of seven strand conductors, isolated by silicone impregnated glass fibres and shielded by a metal braid. The cross section presented an oval form of 1.5mm × 2.0mm.

The first one presented results with a reduced signal quality, due to electrical conductivity of both carbon fibres and metal tooling. The second sensor lead to better signal quality. However, the size of the shielded sensor cannot allow its direct positioning on a laminate without being invasive.

For this project, an innovative approach, flexible thin film sensors on foil, was selected. The sensor consists of two long, parallel metal strands (0.225mm wide each, 0.225mm apart) which comprise the two wires for a differential E-TDR measurement.

They are flanked on both sides by wider metal wires (1.5mm wide each) serving as electrical ground, for reducing the negative effect of surrounding electrically conductive carbon fibres. The four conductor paths are supported by a polyetherimide film (which can be processed at targeted temperatures) and fed to the connector area. Pins, which are coated with gold, are soldered to these four pads and form the interface to the CFF equipment.

A schematic picture of the thin film sensor is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of a thin film sensor

3. EXPERIMENTATION

The thin film CFF sensors test is performed following a vacuum infusion process. Relevant epoxy resin and reinforcement are chosen to be as close as possible to standard aerospace process parameters.

3.1 Thin film sensors

Two thin film sensors, 60cm long each, are investigated within this project. Their respective geometries are described in Table 1.

Sensor 1		Sensor 2	
Material	Thickness	Material	Thickness
Polyetherimide substrate	0.025mm	Polyetherimide substrate	0.05mm
Epoxy adhesive film	0.015mm	Epoxy adhesive film (×2)	0.015mm
Copper line	0.018mm	Copper foil (×2)	0.07mm
Schemes of the sensors sections			

Table 1: Description of evaluated thin film sensors – Schematic representation are to scale

On sensor 2, the copper on the top side is etched to build the geometry depicted in Figure 2. On the bottom side, the copper is not structured. It is left as a foil, is electrically connected to the ground and is used as sensor shielding.

Sensors thicknesses are, respectively, 0.058mm and 0.220mm.

3.2 Equipment

A differential time domain reflectometer with an effective bandwidth of 3.5 GHz, is used for the tests (CFF device from InFactory Solutions, presented in Figure 3). The instrument contains both a fast rise time step impulse generator and a sampling oscilloscope as well as a multiplexing unit. Through the multiplexing unit, it provides four outputs, suitable for

measuring four sensors in single-ended mode or two sensors in differential mode. Both the reflectometer and the multiplexing unit are controlled by an inhouse developed software.

Figure 3: Presentation of the CFF device

3.3 Materials

The resin used for the experiment is an epoxy resin, HexFlow[®] RTM6. It is a common product for aeronautic applications. It is cured at 180°C.

The reinforcement selected is an HiTape[®] UD210 IMA-12K/12.7mm/V800E. It is a dry unidirectional reinforcement, with an areal weight of 210g/m². It is designed for infusion and injection processes, meeting primary structure requirements. It is presented as a tow of 12.7mm width. The preform, 200mm × 900 mm, was built in advance, using a dry fibre placement process, with the following orientations: (-45/0/45/90)_{2s}.

3.4 Test setup

The experiment follows the patented VAP[®] Vacuum Assisted Process [1]. Auxiliary materials are stacked as described in Figure 4 (which includes the sensors position).

Figure 4: Auxiliary materials stacking scheme

The CFF sensors are placed in the centre of the laminates. The thermocouple, 10cm long, is placed between the two thin film sensors. Sensors positioning is described in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Test Set-up

The resin inlet is not perfectly centred along the laminate edge, but is slightly shifted on the left (on the direction of the CFF device). A higher distance between vacuum outlet and resin inlet improves the quality of the fibre impregnation.

3.5 Infusion and cure conditions

The resin is preheated two hours at 70°C. The tool and preform are preheated at 100°C and placed under a vacuum of 0.5mbar. For the infusion, the resin is placed in the oven, at 70°C. The vacuum is kept at 0.5mbar. The infusion starts when opening the resin inlet. It is closed once a full impregnation of the laminate is observed.

During the infusion, both resin flow front (left and right side of the resin inlet) are, in parallel, optically followed. A mark is drawn every 15 seconds, as described in Figure 66.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the optical monitoring of both left and right resin flow front

The cure starts after the end of the infusion. The oven heats up at 2°C/min to 180°C and dwells for 1h45.

The temperature cycle followed by the resin during the tests is described in Figure 77. Infusion and cure temperature are recorded by the integrated thermocouples.

Figure 7: Temperature profile observed by the resin during the test

The temperature difference between resin and preform during infusion leads to the observed perturbations in the recorded temperature.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Resin flow front monitoring

Flow front of the resin, during the infusion, is followed using impedance. Impedance is directly correlated to dielectric permittivity of the environment. Due to the difference of permittivity between resin and reinforcement, the flow front is immediately detected when reaching a point

of the sensor. Profiles of the impedance along the sensor lines are recorded every second. Figure 88 presents the evolution of profiles for both sensor 1 and sensor 2, every 15 seconds, during the infusion.

Figure 8: Evolution of dielectric permittivity during infusion time (left: sensor 1; right: sensor 2)

The resin introduction is clearly identified. It starts at 3 seconds for sensor 2 and 15 seconds for sensor 1, which is coherent with the test set-up (sensor 2 is the closest to resin inlet). The displacement of the resin flow fronts (left and right) are also observed on the impedance profiles.

The sensor without the shielding (sensor 1) presents a higher absolute impedance and a better signal-to-noise ratio than the shielded one (sensor 2). The reason lies in the bigger distance of the conductive strands to any conductive material for sensor 1 due to the omission of the shielding on the back of the sensors. For a homogeneous preform, such as the one infused in this paper, a shielding does not have a positive impact. Furthermore, the thin conductive strands of sensor 1 make this design more subject to high frequency effects and attenuation. However, for an inhomogeneous preform consisting of different materials (glass, carbon) in different areas, a shielding is believed to help to eliminate these changes and facilitate an automated signal evaluation significantly.

Figure 9: Comparison of optical monitoring and CFF sensors monitoring (left: sensor 1; right: sensor 2)

Comparison of both optical and CFF sensors monitoring (presented in Figure 9) is based on the distance between the laminate left side (or CFF device) and the resin flow front. Indeed, for the left flow front, the distance decreases during infusion, while it increases for the right flow front.

For both sensors, the left flow front presents matching results between optical and CFF sensors methods. On the right side, some deviation appears after 2 minutes infusion time. This can be

explained by the length compensation not finalized for those specific sensor geometries (developed for the two first sensor generations).

4.2 Cure monitoring

To follow the resin curing, a specifically designed software transforms the data to obtain the average of each profile during the whole curing time. The resulted graph for sensor 1 and sensor 2 are presented in Figure 10. For a spatial cure monitoring, the profiles can also be split into section, which are evaluated independently. Such an analysis was not carried out in this study.

Figure 10: Evolution of impedance average during curing time for both sensor (grey left scale: sensor 1; blue right scale: sensor 2)

Sensor 1 presents a higher sensitivity, i.e. a larger impedance difference between the uncured and cured state of app. 8Ω compared to 4Ω of sensor 2. The higher sensitivity is caused by the omission of a shielding resulting in a larger distance of the conductors to any conductive materials.

However, sensor 2 also shows more noise and more outliers within the recorded profiles. This is because it is more susceptible to any perturbation coming from the carbon fibre preform, such as relaxation effects caused by the reduced resin viscosity during the heat up. Additionally, as mentioned in section 4.1, the thinner sensor geometry leads to negative high frequency effects.

In parallel, a prediction of the resin cure is developed from a kinetic model. Based on DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry) measurements, the model provides reaction progress prediction for the exact temperature profile observed by the resin (Figure 7).

Impedance results are normalised and compared to the cure prediction.

Figure 11: Comparison of the normalised impedance evolution during curing time with a predictive reaction progress (left: sensor 1; right: sensor 2)

Impedance follows a similar evolution than the reaction progress. However, differences can be observed between the two evaluated sensors. Indeed, the normalised impedance graphs shapes differ in the period 20 to 60 minutes. The reason for this deviation will be further investigated.

There is a possibility, that deformations within the sensor caused by the heating up, lead to slight deviations of the measured dielectric properties. This thesis is backed by the fact, that similar irregularities were not observed with other sensors.

The good correlation however observed is a first step before the mathematical correlation.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The carried-out study shows that, in combination with InFactory's CFF equipment, thin film sensors allow the spatial monitoring of the infusion and cure of composite parts. Through the thin dimensions, they present the benefit of having minimal influence on the layup. With both investigated sensor geometries, the two separate flow fronts within the part could be picked up and the recorded cure curves show a good correlation with the kinetic model.

Always targeting miniaturisation, InFactory Solutions has, since the end of this study, developed a new generation of sensors. The twisted sensors combine a shielding effect with the possibility to achieve very low diameters of 0.1mm. They are less expensive and highly flexible. They also have the advantage of not presenting the slight deviation in the cure curves described in this paper with the thin film geometry.

Further studies will focus on two main topics. First, the development of the evaluation algorithms will help reduce the deviations in the recorded flow front position. Furthermore, mathematical correlation between CFF signal and cure conversion of the resin will be investigated. The aim is to provide in-real time information concerning the final properties of the monitored composite parts.

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